

Slope-Aware Variable Admittance for a Robotic Guide Dog

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Abstract—This extended abstract investigates how terrain slope influences human preferences in physical interaction with a robotic guide dog for visually impaired individuals. A quadruped robot equipped with a rigid handle guides users through haptic feedback while varying admittance control parameters according to slope. We introduce a design combining slope-aware admittance, an energy tank for passivity, path following, and interaction force estimation. A human subjects study with blindfolded participants confirms that stiffness modulation is crucial for safety and comfort, while damping plays a minor role. These results offer design guidelines for future assistive robots.

Index Terms—assistive robotics, robotic guide dog, human-robot interaction, variable admittance

I. INTRODUCTION

Over 2.2 billion people worldwide are blind or visually impaired (BVI) [1]. Traditional aids such as white canes or guide dogs present limitations: canes only detect obstacles upon contact, while guide dogs are expensive (about \$50,000), scarce, and limited in adaptability [2]. Robotic guide dogs are emerging as a viable alternative, offering features such as GPS navigation, AI-based perception, and long-term affordability.

Robots must, however, provide safe and natural haptic interaction through a rigid handle. In the field of walking assistance [3] it was proven that users' preferences in terms of force interaction change as the terrain slope varies. We expand such a concept as a means to improve guidance quality and safety. This work is an excerpt from [4].

II. METHODOLOGY

Our framework combines a passive variable admittance filter, path following, and a momentum-based estimation of the external wrench to provide robotic guidance.

A. Variable Admittance Filter

The robot adapts the linear components of the stiffness and damping parameters of the admittance filter based on the estimated slope. Several variation policies are considered: intuitively we expect that the robot should stick closely to the nominal path uphill to better guide the user, and allow more compliance downhill to avoid excessive forces that may destabilize the human, but we also test a policy opposite to this intuition and a case in which the parameters are constant.

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B. Energy Tank for Passivity

Varying admittance parameters may inject energy into the system. An energy tank monitors energy flow, storing dissipated energy and releasing it for stiffness variation if enough has been stored, or otherwise keeping the stiffness constant if the tank doesn't have enough energy. This guarantees passivity with respect to the pair of the compliant system's velocity and the external wrench, regardless of parameter changes.

C. Path Following

The reference path is defined geometrically with straight and curved segments. The robot continuously updates its reference pose based on proximity to the path, avoiding time-based trajectories that could pull the user excessively if they pause.

D. Momentum-Based Estimator

Interaction forces at geometric center of the robot are estimated without additional sensors by employing a momentum-based observer. This enables measurement of user input while keeping the robot hardware unchanged.

III. HUMAN SUBJECTS STUDY

A commercial quadruped robot (ANYmal D from ANYbotics) was equipped with a rigid handle. Outdoor trials were performed on flat terrain and an 8.5° slope. Fifteen blindfolded participants (mean age 29.07, standard deviation 3.88) interacted with the robot. The factors considered in our experiments are (i) *Path*, the path the robot guides the human on, chosen between uphill, downhill and curve; (ii) *Stiffness*, the strategy for varying the admittance filter's stiffness, increasing it uphill, increasing it downhill or keeping it constant; (iii) *Damping*, following the same options as the stiffness. To avoid having to test all the 27 possible combinations, a Taguchi L_9 design [5, Chapter 4.2] was employed.

Participants performed the nine tests and rated Control (\mathcal{C}), Fatigue (\mathcal{F}), Safety (\mathcal{S}), Aggressiveness (\mathcal{A}), and Frustration (\mathcal{R}). The measure (\mathcal{I}) of how often the interaction force surpassed a set threshold was also analyzed.

A. Results

Table I contains the mean results across all participants for each metric and test, while Tables II-VII show the results of the ANOVA tests, performed following [5, Chapter 4.2].

TABLE I
SCORES ACROSS FACTORS FOR DIFFERENT TESTS

	C	\mathcal{F}	S	A	\mathcal{R}	\mathcal{I}
Test 1	3.40	1.73	3.40	2.80	1.73	0.77
Test 2	4.00	1.40	3.60	2.73	1.53	0.78
Test 3	4.20	1.27	3.67	2.07	1.33	0.71
Test 4	3.07	1.53	3.20	2.93	1.53	0.98
Test 5	3.53	1.47	3.60	2.60	1.73	0.98
Test 6	3.53	1.80	3.53	2.60	1.60	0.97
Test 7	3.93	1.47	4.07	2.13	1.53	0.64
Test 8	4.00	1.13	4.20	2.20	1.13	0.71
Test 9	3.60	1.27	4.07	2.87	1.53	0.79

TABLE II
N-WAY ANOVA ON CONTROL

Source	Sum Sq.	d.f.	Mean Sq.	F	p-value
Path	0.4573	2.0000	0.2286	2.8405	0.2604
Stiffness	0.1788	2.0000	0.0894	1.1104	0.4738
Damping	0.2440	2.0000	0.1220	1.5153	0.3976
Error	0.1610	2.0000	0.0805		
Total	1.0410	8.0000			

TABLE III
N-WAY ANOVA ON FATIGUE

Source	Sum Sq.	d.f.	Mean Sq.	F	p-value
Path	0.1462	2.0000	0.0731	1.5258	0.3959
Stiffness	0.0484	2.0000	0.0242	0.5052	0.6644
Damping	0.0899	2.0000	0.0449	0.9381	0.5160
Error	0.0958	2.0000	0.0479		
Total	0.3802	8.0000			

TABLE IV
N-WAY ANOVA ON SAFETY

Source	Sum Sq.	d.f.	Mean Sq.	F	p-value
Path	0.7654	2.0000	0.3827	193.7500	0.0051
Stiffness	0.0365	2.0000	0.0183	9.2500	0.0976
Damping	0.1017	2.0000	0.0509	25.7500	0.0374
Error	0.0040	2.0000	0.0020		
Total	0.9077	8.0000			

It can be seen that *Path* is weakly significant in C . No factor is significant in \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{R} . *Path* and *Damping* are significant in S , while *Stiffness* is weakly significant. *Stiffness* is weakly significant in A . Finally, *Path* is significant in \mathcal{I} and *Stiffness* is weakly significant.

We can also study which levels, with respect to the significant factors, optimize our metrics. The highest control is achieved on the downhill path, while the curved path minimizes it. Safety (S) is maximized with on the uphill path with stiffness increasing uphill and constant damping, and is instead minimum on the curved path with constant stiffness and damping increasing downhill. Aggressiveness is highest with constant stiffness and lowest with stiffness increasing uphill. Finally \mathcal{I} peaks on the curved path with constant stiffness and reaches its minimum on the uphill path with stiffness increasing uphill.

TABLE V
N-WAY ANOVA ON AGGRESSIVENESS

Source	Sum Sq.	d.f.	Mean Sq.	F	p-value
Path	0.1462	2.0000	0.0731	0.7115	0.5843
Stiffness	0.5017	2.0000	0.2509	2.4423	0.2905
Damping	0.0247	2.0000	0.0123	0.1202	0.8927
Error	0.2054	2.0000	0.1027		
Total	0.8780	8.0000			

TABLE VI
N-WAY ANOVA ON FRUSTRATION

Source	Sum Sq.	d.f.	Mean Sq.	F	p-value
Path	0.0751	2.0000	0.0375	0.4343	0.6972
Stiffness	0.0040	2.0000	0.0020	0.0229	0.9777
Damping	0.0306	2.0000	0.0153	0.1771	0.8495
Error	0.1728	2.0000	0.0864		
Total	0.2825	8.0000			

TABLE VII
N-WAY ANOVA ON INTERACTION

Source	Sum Sq.	d.f.	Mean Sq.	F	p-value
Path	0.1237	2.0000	0.0618	30.4348	0.0318
Stiffness	0.0083	2.0000	0.0042	2.0492	0.3280
Damping	0.0012	2.0000	0.0006	0.2976	0.7706
Error	0.0041	2.0000	0.0020		
Total	0.1373	8.0000			

B. Discussion

These findings confirm the intuition that uphill requires firmer guidance and downhill requires softer interaction. Stiffness modulation emerged as a key factor for improving user safety and minimizing the perceived aggressiveness and the required interaction, while damping played an overall minor role. In general, the framework causes little frustration or mental fatigue regardless of the policy adopted.

IV. FUTURE WORK

Future studies will involve visually impaired participants to validate results beyond blindfolded volunteers. Broader ranges of stiffness values will be explored, including angular admittance adaptation for curved paths, while damping will be kept constant. Finally, integration with navigation features such as obstacle avoidance and voice interaction will move robotic guide dogs closer to real-world deployment.

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